

Table I shows the experimental p_B values and the corresponding values of the functions:

$$a_{A^-} \cdot \frac{C-x}{2C-x} \times 10^3 \text{ and } a_{A^-} \cdot \frac{x}{2C-x} \times 10^3$$

where A^- represents acetate ion and 'x', total concentration of "free acetic acid species"

FIG. 1

(Ordinate magnified 10 times of the abscissa).

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given by $c_{A^-} + C_a$). Fig. 1 represents equation (5b) (vide Part III, *loc. cit.*) graphically (using " $c_{A^-} = a_{A^-}$ " in 5b for solutions of low ionic strengths). The slope and intercept on the ordinate of this straight line curve give the values of k_1 and k_2 as $k_1 = 210.0 \times 10^{-3}$ and $k_2 = 50.0 \times 10^{-3}$. These may be regarded as the average values of ' k_1 ' and ' k_2 ' over the range of ionic strengths employed. In Fig. 1 the circles represent data from Table I for the first 20 solution mixtures (Nos. 1 to 20) in which ' C_a ' is constant and ' C ' varying, and the triangles represent those for the last 9 solution mixtures (Nos. 20 to 29) in which ' C ' is constant and ' C_a ' varies. Table II, in which the values of ' K_1 ' and ' K_2 ' calculated by following the procedure already described, is self-explanatory.

Thanks of the authors are due to Professor S. K. Bhattacharyya, for his interest in the work.

Received August 17, 1957.

SOME ALIPHATIC MONOCARBOXYLATE COMPLEXES OF BIVALENT METALS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION. PART VIII. NICKEL MONO-ACETATO COMPLEX

By S. K. SIDDHANTA AND S. N. BANERJEE

The composition of the complex formed between Ni^{2+} and acetate ions has been found to be $NiAc^+$, from a study of the equilibrium H^+ -concentrations in mixtures of equimolecular nickel nitrate and acetic acid solutions, with the help of "Job's method of continued variation", employing the increase of H^+ -concentration as a new index property.

The thermodynamic dissociation constant, K , for the equilibrium $NiAc^+ \rightleftharpoons Ni^{2+} + Ac^-$ has been found out as 75.9×10^{-3} at $21.3-22.0^\circ$, as in Part I of this series.

The same procedure as adopted in Part I (this *Journal*, 1958, 38, 269) was followed to determine the thermodynamic dissociation constant for the equilibrium,

(where Ac^- represents acetate ion)

$$K = \frac{a_{\text{Ni}^{2+}} \cdot a_{\text{Ac}^-}}{a_{\text{NiAc}^+}} = \frac{c_{\text{Ni}^{2+}} \cdot c_{\text{Ac}^-}}{c_{\text{NiAc}^+}} \cdot \frac{f_{\text{Ni}^{2+}} \cdot f_{\text{Ac}^-}}{f_{\text{NiAc}^+}}, \quad \dots (1)$$

from a study of the p_H of solution mixtures containing '1-x' volume of nickel nitrate and 'x' volume of acetic acid, 'x' varying from 0.1 to 0.9, and both parent solutions being at the same concentration, 'C'. The composition of the complex formed has been determined, as in the case of lead acetate (Part I, *loc. cit.*). From Y-x plots it has been observed that the maximum value of 'Y' corresponds to the reacting proportion 1:1 for nickel nitrate and acetic acid. It is evident therefore that under the condition of the experiment, the following equilibrium alone is most predominant, and the formation of higher complexes, e.g., NiAc_2 , NiAc_3 , etc., is negligible. The reaction thus becomes

EXPERIMENTAL

Nickel nitrate and acetic acid were of A.R. quality. All solutions were prepared with conductivity water. Stock solutions of nickel nitrate and acetic acid were prepared, and in these solutions nickel was determined with dimethylglyoxime and acetic acid, by titration with a standard alkali solution. After keeping the mixtures in a closed room for 4 hours, the p_H values were determined by following the same procedure and observing the same precautions as were done in Part II (*ibid.*, 58, 38, 279).

FIG. 1

TABLE I
(HAc represents acetic acid)

1-x.	Solution mixtures in c.c.			Concentration of parent solutions.			
	HAc.	Ni(NO ₃) ₂ .	H ₂ O.	<i>p</i> _H .	Increase in [H ⁺] (Y × 10 ⁴).	<i>p</i> _H .	Increase in [H ⁺] (Y' × 10 ⁴).
0.1	9	1	...	2.690	5.42	2.882	0.70
	9	...	1	2.824		*(12.42)	
0.2	8	2	...	2.673	6.44	2.882	1.36
	8	...	2	2.830		(11.76)	
0.3	7	3	...	2.673	7.17	2.887	1.91
	7	...	3	2.852		(11.06)	
0.4	6	4	...	2.673	8.32	2.897	2.54
	6	...	4	2.889		(10.14)	
0.5	5	5	...	2.690	8.40	2.928	2.55
	5	...	5	2.920		(9.25)	
0.6	4	6	...	2.724	8.32	2.964	2.62
	4	...	6	2.980		(8.24)	
0.7	3	7	...	2.767	7.98	3.007	2.66
	3	...	7	3.040		(7.18)	
0.8	2	8	...	2.830	7.51	3.079	2.54
	2	...	8	3.138		(5.80)	
0.9	1	9	...	2.957	6.11	3.226	1.84
	1	...	9	3.307		(4.10)	

N. B. In the present case the hydrogen-ion concentration of the mixture of '1-x' c.c. of nickel nitrate solution at concentrations $C=0.2$ and $C=0.1$ with 'x' c.c. of water is very small and has therefore been neglected in calculating the value of 'Y'.

* In this case with $C=0.1$, the $[H^+]$ ($\approx a_H^+ \times 10^4$) for the acetic acid solutions are calculated from the relations,

$$K_a = \frac{Ca^2}{1-a} \quad \text{and} \quad [H^+] = aC,$$

where a is the degree of dissociation of acetic acid; C is the concentration of acetic acid and K_a , the ionisation constant of acetic acid at 22° (1.75×10^{-5} from "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions" by Harned and Owen, 2nd. ed., p. 580). These values are shown in parentheses.

TABLE II

The symbols used in the table headings and their evaluations are same as in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

1-x.	Solution mixtures in c.c.		Concentration of parent solutions.			
	HAc.	Ni(NO ₃) ₂ .	μ .	$K \times 10^3$.	μ .	$K \times 10^3$.
0.1	9	1	0.0610	17.56	0.0310	35.76
0.2	8	2	0.1205	11.80	0.0607	23.69
0.3	7	3	0.1801	8.96	0.0903	16.83
0.4	6	4	0.2398	6.42	0.1203	13.11
0.5	5	5	0.2996	5.05	0.1503	12.07
0.6	4	6	0.3596	4.27	0.1802	10.47
0.7	3	7	0.4195	3.33	0.2100	8.37
0.8	2	8	0.4794	2.53	0.2399	6.91
0.9	1	9	0.5395	1.87	0.2699	6.09

N. B. Taken ionisation constant of acetic acid to be 1.75×10^{-5} (Harned and Owen, *loc. cit.*).

The results of p_x determinations for mixtures of two sets of equimolar parent solutions of nickel nitrate and acetic acid, one having concentration $C=0.2$ and another set $C=0.1$, have been shown in Table I.

FIG. 2

(The sign $\square$ represents the plot of pK_2/μ from Table II of part IX).

The values of 'Y' against the corresponding values of 'x' from Table I, for mixtures of nickel nitrate and acetic acid solutions, both being at concentration $C=0.2M$, have been graphically represented by curve I, and those for both parent solutions at concentration $C=0.1M$, by curve II, in Fig. 1. The values of ' μ ' and ' K ' for the solution mixtures, studied in the present work, have been obtained by following the same procedure as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*) and these are shown in Table II. As in the previous case (vide Part I), the plot of ' K ' against ' μ ' from Table II yields a smooth curve, which has not been used to evaluate the value of ' K ' by extrapolation to zero ionic strength. In Fig. 2, the graph $pK (= -\log K)$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ from Table II gives a straight line curve which on extrapolation to $\sqrt{\mu}=0$ gives the value of pK corresponding to the true thermodynamic constant, K . These values of ' pK ' and ' K ' at $\sqrt{\mu}=0$ are 1.12 and 75.9×10^{-3} at $21.3-22^\circ$ respectively.

Critical comments on the previous work on the subject, as also on the present work have been made in Part IX of this series.

The authors' best thanks are due to Prof. S. K. Bhattacharyya for offering all the facilities to do this work.

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p_x values of aqueous solution mixtures of nickel acetate and nitric acid at different concentrations, after attainment of equilibrium, have been determined and the data obtained have been utilised to calculate the mass action constants, K_1 and K_2 , for the two successive equilibria, $NiAc_2 \rightleftharpoons NiAc^+ + Ac^-$ and $NiAc^+ \rightleftharpoons Ni^{2+} + Ac^-$, by applying Bjerrum's method. The inapplicability of the method of Siddhanta and Banerjee (Part III) has been accounted for and a method has been suggested to calculate the values of thermodynamic dissociation constants, K_1 and K_2 , in a similar way as described in Part VII of the series.